

Towards the Eco-Digital: Real-Time Animation with Plants, Data and Sound

Dr. Rewa Wright
UnCalculated Studio
Meanjin/Brisbane, QLD, Australia
rewa.wright@qut.edu.au

Simon Howden
UnCalculated Studio
Meanjin/Brisbane, Australia
simonhowden@hotmail.com

Mereana Wright-Osborne
UnCalculated Studio
Meanjin/Brisbane, Australia

Figure 1: Still from audio-reactive animation generated by plant signals, UnCalculated Studio 2023.

Abstract

The 'eco-digital' is an area of artistic research that explores the intersection of digital technology and ecological themes. Often artists are looking at how art can help highlight the climate crisis, motivating the public to act. Combining digital art practices, such as computer animation, virtual reality, and generative art, with a focus on ecological issues, eco-digital art invites and encourages discourse on a wide range of environmental sustainability, biodiversity, and the relationship between technology and nature. In this intersectional domain, animation can play a valuable role, creating new approaches that reflect, critique, and even propose solutions to contemporary environmental challenges. The eco-digital approach emphasizes the integration of natural processes and digital aesthetics to foster a deeper understanding of and engagement with the natural world. Working at the intersection of animation, sound, installation and data visualisation, we explore ways that digital systems and ecological systems can interact, drawing attention to the common threads that link both humans and plants. This is possible through a variety of methods and techniques: this research examines one such approach, combining plant bio-electrical signals, Indigenous thinking, human music and real time animation. Our goal is to develop approaches that might benefit future hybrid ecosystems, incorporating Indigenous practices of environmental care that mobilise animation and operate to bring the public closer to nature.

CCS Concepts

• mātauranga Māori (Māori knowledge) , plant bio-electrical signals, real-time animation, beyond human, software assemblage;

Keywords

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Figure 2: Still images from 'He Koiira o te Wa: biology of Time' by UnCalculated Studio

1 Introduction

Before focussing on animation, we establish a context for exploring plant energies in art. Artistic mobilizations of plant energies have varied approaches, from aesthetic to conceptual and genetic. Notable works include Nam June Paik's *TV Garden* (1974), Olafur Eliasson's *Forked Forest Path* (1998), and John Cage's *Child of Tree* (1975). These pieces demonstrate different methods of integrating plants into art, ranging from sculptural elements to bio-electrical signal sonification. John Baldessari's conceptual video *Teaching a Plant the Alphabet* (1972) critiques the human desire to communicate with plants, illustrating the perceived thresholds between human and plant life. Prue Gibson (2018) notes a shift in artistic practice where plants are no longer treated as aesthetic material but as agents with their own particular agency. Works by Natalie Jeremijenko, Eduardo Kac, Laura Beloff, and Jonas Jørgensen explore genetic and signal-based interactions with plants, probing the capacities of a plant's calcium sensing system. These projects highlight the co-compositional potential of human-plant relations, where plants are active elements rather than passive objects. Sommerer and Mignonneau's *Interactive Plant Growing* (1992) allows participants to touch real plants to trigger digital plant growth on screen. This interaction requires a combination of tactile micro-gestures, emphasizing a thoughtful exploration and sensitivity to real plants. Gregory Lasserre and Anais met den Ancxt's *Akoumaflore* (2007-present) uses sensors to detect bio-electric potentials in plants, converting these signals into sound through human touch. These artworks underscore the active participation of plants in art, extending human-plant relations to recognize their embodied modes of agency.

2 Beyond human animation

We are accustomed to thinking of artificial intelligence and machine learning as the algorithmic forces that operate to expand animation beyond the human. However, we need to also acknowledge the 'beyond human' potential already embedded in the multifarious embodied connections within nature itself. How can we leverage animation to generate new connections that bring humans and ecology closer together. If we can foster, on the 'human side' enhanced relations of care and responsibility, then this might help to draw attention to the unfolding climate crisis. Blanche Verlie notes that human emotions entangle with climate change, causing anxiety but latent with inherent potential for social transformation (Verlie 2021).

One approach to fostering social transformation and fuel action, could be to deploy animation as not only a communication medium, but as a medium that actively makes embodied connections between human and nonhuman actors (in this case, living plants). To offer a productive alternative to simply 'representing' plants using animation, we examined the concept of the Body Area Network (BAN). In engineering, BAN research, investigates the human body as a transmission channel for data, where the bio-electrical charges that circulate in fields around the surface of the skin are harnessed as energy sources able to power wearable devices (Zimmerman 1995; Fujii and Okumura 2012). In the performance practice of laser koto musician and BAN interface designer Miya Masaoka, we find an exciting experimental trajectory that modulates plants, data and the human body. Since the 1990s, Masaoka has worked intensively with plants as co-composers, creating ensemble musical pieces for live performance. Her initial plant-human interfaces – a type of BAN established to sense physiological electrical data near the body – were developed with BAN pioneer Tom Zimmerman. These incorporate body-plant-energy networks to generate live musical performances as well as scored compositions.

In performances such as *Pieces for Plants* (2000-2012)[i], Masaoka networked a specially prepared philodendron by attaching electrodes to its leaves, to react in concert with electrical fields around her body. Using the BAN as an unstable formation, Masaoka modulated with the emergent energy fields. Masaoka has shared her perspective on plants as responsive entities: "Working with plants in my studio, I was astonished by their ability to respond consistently to my walking in and out of the room ... I [became] increasingly aware of the sensitivity of the plant, and gained greater empathy and awareness of their behaviour, needs and responses" (Miya Masaoka 2018).[ii] Clearly, Masaoka considers the responses and behaviour from plants as an element that affectively co-composes the sound piece, citing their ability to emit different signals according to their environment. Masaoka's creative use of BAN's can be thought of as ways to pose provocations to the practice of augmented audio, and how that can be interconnected with real-time animation to foreground a blend of plant and human bio-electrical signals.

2.1 human/nonhuman entanglement and life force

Animation practices influenced by philosophical understandings extending beyond the human—such as posthuman and post-Anthropocene approaches—partially connect with ancient perspectives of an expanded nature that encompasses both human and nonhuman kin. These perspectives are preserved in Indigenous epistemologies like *mātauranga Māori* (Māori knowledge). The [anonymous] co-author's relationship with plants is informed by Māori ancestry, where the organic kingdom coexists with humans in a radical cosmological contingency. The concept of 'mauri', meaning 'life force' in *te reo Māori*, and the practice of 'kaitiakitanga', or guardianship, nurture familial relations of care between human and nonhuman actors. Since 'mauri/life force' emanates through all human and nonhuman actors, this is a mode of entanglement that can highlight commonalities of being and becoming. This perspective challenges the artificial separation of nature and culture, promoting new configurations of care and mutual ethical responsibility. Taking a

perspective of care and filtering this through expanded animation practice, affords the opportunity to re-formulate relations with the nonhuman, plants and algorithms.

'Performative interfacing', a live technique developed in our real-time animation practice by since 2016, generates entanglements between human gestures, plant signals, and computational networks. In the installation 'He Koiira o te Wa: Biology of Time', traditional choreographic techniques (improvised hand gestures, body movements) engage relational movements of the body with plant-data networks. Created in Touch Designer, the real-time animations are triggered by living plants as co-composers to the installation experience. Human music plays alongside the plant 'music', and plant signals start the network. Participants (sometimes human performers or audience) can gently touch the plants to join their body signals with those of the plants. Responsive to touch, electrical potentials are converted to MIDI and then added to an audio-reactive network. This tactile network is micro-temporal as well as 'phenological' (ie in the time and rhythm of the seasons). As suggested by the name 'Biology of Time'; this artwork examines different modes of time, and how we intra-act across temporal realities. Human, computational and plant time are radically different modalities, and this is demonstrated in the erratic rhythmic quality of the real-time sonics. Intra-actions in data, emerging from plant signals, interact with human gestures, leading to improvisational performances where plants act as co-composers. This work highlights plants' bio-electrical responsiveness to environmental stimuli, positioning them as active participants in the creative process. 'Performative interfacing' and tactile connections with plant sonics, are speculative methods that highlight the potential of real-time animation in eco-digital arts practice.

Thinking through Karen Barad's notion of 'intra-actions', the use of tactile connections to modulate plant signals and generate real-time animation becomes a method that can create an embodied connection between humans and plants. Bringing Barad's understanding of matter as intra-active to bear on augmented material has led more generally to an approach where augments are considered as intra-active forces that coalesce with other modalities of matter, such as the corporeal body, infrared and the bio-electrical signals from living plants. This perspective also engages diffraction as a process which generates patterns of interference, through the relational forces exerted on one mode of matter— digital, flesh or plant — by another. Recent work by UnCalculated Studio engages two temporal registers: the micro-temporal register of machines, and the phenological register of plants. In the micro-temporal register of machines, decisions by software operate outside of the threshold of human perception, yet nonetheless influence human movement and action. Both phenological and micro-temporal registers are engaged as the plant signals, captured through MIDI, influence the movements, aesthetic and formal qualities of geometry, shaders and colours in Touch Designer. Our process also involves, from time to time, recording in the 'wild', outside of the controlled studio environment. We have recorded plant signals live at various locations, including the bush of Aotearoa/New Zealand (Te Tai Tokerau region) and the famous yucca varietal's endemic to Joshua tree, Palm Desert. Once recorded, these signals are sonified during post-production in the Studio.

3 Plants as Co-Composers

Figure 3: Recording plant signals at Joshua Tree, Palm Desert, CA.

Nga manawataki o te koiira: Biorhythms (2022-3) is a projection mapping and installation piece examining life's pulse through bio-electrical plant signals, data visualization, and composed music. This piece, performed in immersive environments, evokes Māori cultural heritage through computational abstraction. Curvilinear forms inspired by traditional arts transform into pixel topologies, challenging Western pictorial traditions and decolonizing digital tools. Plants are considered co-composers, blending their bio-rhythms with human-produced electronic music, creating a syncretic entanglement of human and nonhuman kin. Indigenous thought opens space for meaning beyond the empirical, destabilizing colonial systems of thought. This research explores new intra-actions alongside computational frameworks, contributing to decolonial art by integrating Indigenous and Western epistemologies.

This research bridges artistic practice with networked technologies and Indigenous epistemologies, emphasizing co-composition with plants and the eco-digital framework. By integrating mātauranga Māori and Western thought, this work challenges traditional boundaries and offers new perspectives on human-nonhuman entanglements. As well, it contributes to eco-digital arts practice by envisioning an Indigenous informed future where real-time animation can contribute to emergent methods of environmental care.

Figure 4: installation view from 'Nga Manawataki o te Koiora: Biorhythms', by Rewa Wright and Simon Howden, the Cube, QUT Gardens' Point Campus, Meanjin/Brisbane during ISEA2024 21-29 June 2024

4 Acknowledgments

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